

INFINITE

BUILDINGRENOVATION

Industrialised envelope solutions

D3.5

Methods for an improved industrialized envelope design

Public Report

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About the project

Prefabrication of multifunctional envelopes has been shown to be a technically-viable approach to increase the rate and quality of residential building deep renovation. However, still several barriers are preventing a massive adoption of such renovation method. Key obstacles for such renovation approach include high design efforts and low design freedom, high investment costs, lack of technical flexibility of the technologies, lack of critical mass activation at the demand side, uncertainty in the market potential, sub-optimised value-chain still based on the traditional renovation, lack of hard-fact knowledge dissemination.

The current digitalisation trends in other markets (i.e. Industry4.0), the exploitation of the industrial capabilities and the experiences of the 1st generation of multifunctional prefabricated envelopes are the three base elements INFINITE relies upon to disruptively change the building renovation sector, finally acting towards a full building stock decarbonisation. Hence, INFINITE proposes a so-called "Renovation4.0" approach, leveraging on the advantages of the "digitalisation and industrialisation coupling" to boost the building renovation sector.

This will allow to keep a tailor-made approach with many design freedom, decrease retrofit costs and time thanks to the overall system and value-chain optimisations and foster the adoption of a broad sustainability driver in terms of eco-compatible long-lasting products and systems. Furthermore, INFINITE promotes the life cycle approach for comprehensive design and optimisation of the O&M and end-of-life residual value depletion, already in the design early stages.

The INFINITE project aims at transferring the Renovation4.0 to the market, developing

- a set of multi-user and multidisciplinary design tools,
- process-optimised all-in-one industrialised eco envelope kits,
- adaptive control systems,
- set of demand- and industry-side matched business models to show the Renovation4.0 market potential,
- a structured framework of entities and knowledge able to clearly and widely demonstrate the Renovation4.0 benefits.

Finally, INFINITE will work to reduce the systems costs, meeting the demand side requirements, engaging all the stakeholders on the value-chain in the developments. As an impact, INFINITE results will be able to increase the market penetration of sustainable, high-quality and long-lasting building retrofitting. INFINITE partners cover the whole renovation process value-chain and will develop the new generation of the residential building renovation actions, based on an all-in-one industrialised Life-Cycle-based approach.

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Acronyms

AM	Adaptive Management
BAMB	Buildings as Material Banks
BCI	Building Circularity Indicator
BNB	Assessment System for Sustainable Building
BREEAM	Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method
C2C	Cradle to Cradle (certification)
CCD	Charge Coupled Device (image sensor in camera)
CCEF	Circular Construction Evaluation Framework
CI	Circularity Indicators
CMOS	Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor (image sensor in camera)
CSA	Canadian Standards Association
D-DAS	Disassembly and Deconstruction Analytics System
DfA/ DfD	Design for Assembly/Disassembly
DGBC	Dutch Green Building Council
DGNB	German Sustainable Building Council
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
GCP	Ground Control Points
GCS	Ground Control Station
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GSD	Ground Sample Distance
IR	Intermediate Range (3D Scanner Surphaser)
JIT	Just in Time
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
LCC	Life Cycle Cost
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
MCDA	Multi Criteria Decision Analysis
MCI	Material Circularity Indicator
MI	Material Index
MIM	Environmental Impact Monitor
RBIM	Reversible BIM (plugin)
RI	Reusability Index
SR	Short Range (3D Scanner Surphaser)
TLS	Terrestrial Laser Scanner
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UAS	Unmanned Aerial System
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

Executive Summary

This report concerns available methodologies for an improved industrialized envelope design. The task focuses on enhancing industrialized renovations through two key aspects in the renovation process: **high-precision 3D geometry scanning and methodologies for Design for Assembly and Disassembly (DfA/DfD)**. The objective is to consolidate state-of-the-art methods, identify key challenges, and provide recommendations for implementation that enhance industrialized retrofit solutions, based on the INFINITE partners experiences in the project.

The first section of the document explores advanced geomatics techniques, particularly laser scanning and digital photogrammetry, as fundamental tools for high-precision surveying in deep renovation. These methods enable accurate building documentation and integration into BIM workflows and facilitate informed decision-making in pre-design and design phases for precise retrofit planning and execution. Based on this finding, a hybrid approach combining laser scanning for high-accuracy geometry capture and digital photogrammetry for broader detailed reconstruction is recommended, with method selection tailored to project-specific requirements. However, current observed limitations, such as a reliance on manual processing for BIM integration, underscore a need for further developments to streamline and scale industrialized retrofit processes.

The second section of the document examines methodologies for DFA/D through state-of-the-art research and a workshop with the INFINITE kit developers, emphasizing flexibility in design strategies to accommodate diverse building contexts. It covers tools and strategies that support modularity, ease of maintenance, and long-term sustainability, and aims to aid the selection of appropriate tools and methods for industrial retrofit development processes. A key outcome is the identification of suitable tools such as Drive 0 for early-stage design evaluation and R-BIM for detailed reversibility assessments in BIM models. The report also emphasizes the need for standardization, integration of circularity assessment methods in BIM workflows, and incentivization of sustainable construction practices.

Findings from the market research and workshops indicate that while promising technologies exist, further development is needed to realize the full potential of industrialized retrofits. Automating the conversion of point cloud data into BIM elements would greatly enhance efficiency in what remains a labor-intensive process. Additionally, improving the interoperability of DfA/D tools with BIM and establishing industry-wide benchmarks for circularity assessments would facilitate the adoption of circular design principles. Integrating these innovations into the renovation workflow will significantly enhance the feasibility, scalability, and impact of industrialized renovation processes.

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction

To enhance both the scale and impact of deep renovation of the EU building stock, supporting the EU renovation wave, industrialized renovation solutions should be actively promoted and implemented. This requires the development of supporting methods and tools, designed from a Life-Cycle perspective. INFINITE focuses on three key areas of development to drive this transformation:

1. A multi-user, interdisciplinary design environment, based on BIM,
2. A new simplified LCA and LCC tool for the all-in industrialized renovation kits to increase awareness of sustainability performance in the renovation market.
3. Methodologies for improving the technological design of renovation kits, developed in INFINITE (WP4), specifically regarding geometry audits (i.e. advanced geomatics) and the design for assembly and disassembly.

This report concerns the third aspect. While the first two items result in digital plugins for an industrialized renovation process, the methodologies for technological design improvements of the renovation kits will not lead to any technical plugins. It aims at contributing to both the technical development (conducted in WP4) and the demonstration building renovation process (deployed in WP6) by highlighting potential improvements in the design process, focusing on the role of advanced geomatics and the design for assembly and disassembly.

The report is structured on two primary areas crucial for effective industrialized renovation:

- **Advanced geomatics and high-precision 3D scanning techniques** (section 2), essential for capturing detailed building geometries and integrating them into BIM workflows.
- **Design for Assembly and Disassembly (DfA/DfD) strategies** (section 3), facilitating modularity, adaptability, and circular economy principles in renovation processes.

By evaluating state-of-the-art technologies, methodologies, and tools, this document identifies key challenges and opportunities in industrialized retrofitting and sets some guidelines and recommendations for both kit developers (WP4) and the demonstrators (WP6).

2 Methodologies to improve high precision geometry 3D phase

2.1 Introduction

Industrialized renovation relies on line-production systems for modular renovation elements. These systems enable the efficient production of both customized units ('series of 1') and large series of the same product, seamlessly integrating mass customization principles to support prefabrication for deep retrofitting of homes. This approach tailors renovation components to individual needs while maintaining the speed and cost-efficiency of mass production

The process is driven by **advanced automation**, generating precise production instructions - in the form of Computerized Numeric Control (CNC) Instructions - from **BIM (Building Information Model)** and **in-situ measurements** to ensure the components produced fit perfectly with the existing structure.

The system is carefully managed using a **smart software** that supports key operations such as **Line-Balancing and Just-In-Time (JIT) manufacturing** and optimizes workflow, enabling flexibility and scalability in producing both simple and complex products across various renovation projects

By combining high-level automation with design customization, this system streamlines the process of retrofitting homes, making it faster, more cost-effective, and adaptable to individual needs. **Plant management** software further supports **line balancing**, scalability in product complexity, and multiple product-market combinations.

A prominent example of this in practice is Bryden Wood's approach to industrialized construction, applying a **Platform-based, modular design system, highly-digitalized production** (often integrating **advanced digital tools** like **BIM, parametric design, and automation**), **JIT** and **advanced production technologies** (like CNC machining and robotic machining of production lines). Their emphasis is on developing **standardized platforms** (such as the modular INFINITE kits or component systems) that can accommodate a degree of customization, rather than fully-individualized units.

Key elements required to steer the fully automated production lines include:

- the application of advanced geomatics, i.e. high precision geometry audits,
- the transfer of the advanced geomatics outputs into BIM (point cloud to BIM),
- the utilization of BIM to steer and control automated production lines.

Geomatics, officially defined as the 'mathematics of the Earth', is the science of collecting, processing, analyzing and interpreting geospatial data. Various instruments and techniques are available for data collection and processing, which play a crucial role in ensuring the needed accuracy and efficiency in building renovation projects.

This section gives an overview of geomatics and high precision geometry techniques applicable to building renovation, highlighting the advantages of their integration into different project phases. A solid understanding of these techniques leads to better-defined project requirements for surveyors and the cost optimization of the geomatics work, such as surveying, data processing, and information transfer into desired software in appropriate format (i.e. BIM-compatible formats).

One of the major bottlenecks in industrialized renovation is the transfer of point clouds to BIM, which **remains a labor-intensive and time-consuming process**. This challenge, however, falls beyond the scope of the INFINITE project. Nevertheless, it represents a critical step towards further automation and Industrialization, and cost reductions. Overcoming this challenge would enable disruptive price reductions without compromising quality.

2.2 Technologies and methodologies for advanced geomatics

When utilizing prefabricated modular elements for façade renovation, the quality of building documentation is crucial.

Figure 1 shows a classification of the geomatics techniques for 3D-data acquisition based on the scene size and complexity of the reconstructed digital model. Surveying techniques to be implemented in the context of INFINITE mainly consist of laser scanning and photogrammetry. These techniques have replaced traditional surveying techniques in many applications. Traditional recording methods based on hand recordings (e.g. by means of tape measurement) are too subjective, time-consuming, and limited in applicability to small-scale projects. Terrestrial surveying and analytical photogrammetry require manual interpretation to derive objects' representations. Whereas new automatic recording methods allow an automated dense sampling of the object surface within a short time (Pfeifer; Briese, 2007), enabled by the speed of acquiring high-density data and highly automated processing, and are used to obtain a 3D model of the building of interest.

Figure 1: Geomatics techniques for 3D data acquisition, shown according to the object/scene dimensions and complexity of the reconstructed digital model (Remondino; Campana, 2014)

2.2.1 Laser scanning

Laser scanning (or LiDAR) is an **active sensing** technique that emits a laser beam in a known direction and records reflections to determine distances. Correlating the distance recorded to the laser's direction enables 3D data acquisition of surface locations. By systematically scanning an object's surface at high resolution (more than 200,000 points per second), laser scanners generate precise high-density 3D sampling of the object surface. The detail level of the resulting 3D model depends on the setting of the scan resolution and the distance to the object.

Different principles can be used to measure the distance between sensor systems and the target objects. They differ in precision, but all have their justification for a certain envelope range.

Two primary measurement principles are applied in building documentation:

- **Pulse-based systems:** large ranges (>100m) can be probed using the 'pulse round trip time measurement principle' to obtain accuracy up to 1 centimeter.
- **Phase-shift systems:** shorter distances (up to 100m) can be measured faster and more accurately (up to 1 millimeter) with the phase-based measurement technique.

The primary output of laser scanning is a point cloud – a set of data points in a user-defined coordinate system that represents an external surface of the scanned object - which serves as basis for BIM integration. Software for pre-processing and exporting point clouds is typically provided along with the scanning system. The main advantage of Laser Scanning over Digital Photogrammetry is that scanners deliver 3D data directly for derivation, thus reducing processing steps.

Laser Scanning Equipment Examples

Table 1 compares selected Terrestrial Laser Scanners (TLSs) relevant for the INFINITE project and for the Industrialised renovation approach. TLSs are tripod-mounted scanners set at a fixed point in the vicinity of the scanned object. They give more accurate results relative to mobile scanners, such as hand-held or vehicle-mounted, and are widely used in surveying large objects, such as buildings.

The four selected examples below are provided by companies with well-established market positions and demonstrated expertise in the field, Faro, Trimble, and Surphaser. The listed companies provide distribution in the EU, along with needed training, knowledge-sharing, and support, and are known for their active engagement in R&D for the continuous improvement of their technology.

Table 1: Comparison of laser scanners based on range, accuracy and features.

	Faro Focus Premium	Trimble X9	Trimble X12	Surphaser 100HSX (SR Short range, IR Intermediate Range)
Image				
Scanner Type	Phase Shift technology	High speed, digital time-of-flight distance measurement with 360° x 282° field of view	High speed, digital time-of-flight distance measurement with 360° x 282° field of view	Phase Shift, Hemispherical Scanner with 360° x 270° field of view
Work Range	0.5 to 150 m (Premium 150) 0.5 to 350 m (Premium 350) 0.5 to 400 m (Premium Max)	0.6 to 80m (Core) 0.6 to 150m (Premium)	0.3 to 250m, 365m (ambiguity interval)	1 to 50m, 90m (ambiguity interval) (For IR HS, recommended)
Measurement Speed	up to 2,000,000 points/second	1,000,000 points/second	2,200,000 points/second	208,000 – 800,000 points/second
Range Uncertainty	1mm	2mm	<1.2mm @ 20m (<1mm + 10ppm)	0.7mm @ 15m
Range Noise (2% reflectivity)	1.2mm @ 25m	<1.5mm @ 30m (80% albedo)	0.25mm @ 25m (136 kHz)	0.3mm @ 10m
Laser class	Class 1	Class 1	Class 1	Class 3R
Size	230mm x 183mm x 103mm	178mm x 353mm x 170mm	150mm x 258mm x 328mm	381mm x 219mm x 120mm

Weight	4.4kg including battery	6.045kg including battery	7.7kg including battery	11kg
Features	<p>Key Features: Dual Axis Compensator, Height Sensor, Compass, GNSS, Integrated camera, Integrated SSD storage, Scanner control through app or on Focus Premium device.</p> <p>Software options: FARO Stream mobile app, FARO Sphere XG cloud-based collaboration platform</p>	<p>Key features: 3D visualization, Automatic calibration, auto in-field IMU-assisted registration, self-levelling, georeferencing, laser pointing</p> <p>Software options: Trimble Perspective Mobile app, Trimble Perspective Software</p>	<p>Key features: 3D visualization, Auto in-field cloud-based registration, georeferencing, laser pointing</p> <p>Software options: Trimble Perspective Mobile app, Trimble Perspective Software, RealWorks, 3DScanning</p>	<p>Standard Accessories: Built-in Scan Controller</p> <p>Optional Accessories: External camera system 60MP equivalent</p>
Links	<p>Link to brochure</p> <p>Link to brochure</p> <p>Link to product website</p>	<p>Link to specs sheet</p> <p>Link to product website</p>	<p>Link to specs sheet</p> <p>Link to product website</p>	<p>Link to brochure</p> <p>Link to product website</p>

Application

Compared to the scanners detailed above, scanner options with higher accuracy and ranges are available, but are typically used for specific applications such as topological surveys, infrastructure surveys, etc.

For building applications, the listed TLSs provide sufficient range and accuracy. They are ideal for both indoor and outdoor scanning, making them well-suited for building renovation and retrofitting projects. The resulting 3D point cloud is directly compatible with BIM workflows, enhancing accuracy and efficiency.

Limitations

Although laser scanners offer high-accuracy data, their main limitations are:

- **High equipment costs and expertise requirements:** equipment costs between €20,000 to €100,000 (O'Neill, 2020) and requires professional expertise to operate, making it expensive to invest in for individual refurbishment projects (Uotila et al., 2021). Such equipment is typically used by specialized companies that provide these services. It could then be potentially integrated into the renovation process through service providers with the necessary role and expertise.
- **Limited scanning capability for larger project:** typically operated from the ground, laser scanners may face challenges in scanning taller buildings and roofs. As a result, complete scans of such buildings typically require complementing laser systems with UAV-mounted scanner to cover more surfaces.
- **Sensitivity to ambient temperature and lighting conditions:** as 3D scanners detect laser to record data, ambient light blending with the laser may interfere with the scan's accuracy (*Advantages & Disadvantages of 3D Laser Scanning*, 2020). Uotila and al. (2021) reports that laser scanner operators face challenges under extreme summer and winter conditions, that may hamper the readings.

Recommendations

Laser scanning is optimal for capturing complex geometries with high accuracy, particularly for low-rise structures. It thus works well when single- or double-storied buildings (i.e. row houses) need to be accurately measured.

For the INFINITE project, due to the wide range of building types covered, its application should be considered selectively based on project requirements as it may be restrictive.

2.2.2 Digital photogrammetry

Digital photogrammetry, as a passive sensing method, reconstructs 3D models using overlapping 2D images from passive sensors, such as digital cameras. Similarly to human vision, it derives depth information from at least two images taken from different angles of the same static scene or object. If an object appears in multiple images, its different relative positions in the images create a stereoscopic view, enabling the derivation of 3D information for the images' overlapping areas.

By automatically identifying common points across images—often thousands per second, depending on computing power—a digital photogrammetric system generates a digital 3D model of the scene. A key parameter influencing the model's detail is the Ground Sample Distance (GSD), which represents the smallest element in the object space distinguishable by the sensor. A larger GSD value results in lower spatial resolution, reducing visible details in the final model.

A major advantage of photogrammetry is that the captured images contain all the necessary data for 3D reconstruction along with photorealistic documentation. Additionally, the method's equipment is cost-effective, as digital cameras are widely available, affordable, and portable.

Digital Photogrammetry Image sensors

Various types of photogrammetric sensors are categorized based on their operational format and application. The following categories outline the main types of sensors used for 3D data acquisition:

- **Terrestrial sensors:** these sensors operating from ground level are ideal for detailed building documentation. They can be of various types and configurations: single CCD/CMOS sensors, frame cameras, linear array sensors, multiple head systems. SLR-type, industrial, consumer, high-speed, panoramic head, etc. Their resolution ranges from lower-cost 10/15 MP cameras to higher-cost more professional 40MP¹ cameras.
- **Aerial sensors:** mounted on UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) or full-scale aircraft, these sensors capture data from above, making them convenient for mapping tall buildings and roofs. A UAS (Unmanned Aerial System) consists of the combination of the aerial vehicle/platform (UAV), the held sensors and a Ground Control Station (GCS) for operation and data processing.
- **Satellite sensors:** operating from space, these sensors provide large-scale terrain and urban mapping. They capture high-resolution imagery using multi-spectral and panchromatic imaging techniques, which are useful for city planning, environmental monitoring and infrastructure assessment.

¹ MegaPixel

Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) types

Since photogrammetry relies on high-quality imagery, UAVs such as drones can be highly-effective for capturing images in hard-to-reach areas like tall building façades and roofscapes. The two primary types of UAVs used in photogrammetry are:

- Fixed wing UAVs: Ideal for covering large areas efficiently with longer flight times.
- Rotary UAVs (multi-rotor drones): Capable of hovering in place and manoeuvring in all directions, making them particularly useful for detailed inspections and close-range photogrammetry.

Due to potential use of UAVs, many countries enforce strict regulations on their operations, typically based on size, weight, flight height, and onboard technology. As of December 31, 2020, a unified EU regulation (EU 2019/947) categorizes UAV operations into three groups:

1. Open - low risk, no special operational authorization required; limited to 120m flight altitude and 25 kg take-off weight.
2. Specific - moderate risk, requiring operational authorization.
3. Certified - high risk, requiring both drone and operator certification.

Most UAVs suitable for structural or architectural surveys fall under the 'Specific' category, as they often exceed the 'Open' weight limits or require permission to fly 'Beyond Visual Line of Sight' (BVLOS) (*Drone Regulations for 2021 and Beyond*, 2021). Consequently, only registered surveyors operating in compliance with these regulations must be appointed to conduct UAV-based surveys.

Workflow

Unlike active range sensors (e.g., laser scanners) that directly capture 3D data, the main objective of photogrammetry is to derive a 3D point cloud from a set of images. The workflow aims to extract metric and accurate 3D information through a structured process consisting of **camera calibration**, **image orientation**, and **point cloud generation**, followed by optional steps such as **3D measurement**, **structuring**, **modelling**, **texture mapping**, and **visualization**.

Camera calibration and image orientation are crucial for obtaining precise 3D geometric information from 2D images. Camera calibration determines the camera's internal parameters, including focal length, principal point, and lens distortion. Meanwhile, image orientation defines the external parameters, such as the position and angular orientation of the camera when capturing images. These steps can be performed separately or combined using the same dataset and processing method.

To align the model with a specific coordinate system, additional measurements are required to establish scale, position, and orientation. This is typically achieved using Ground Control Points (GCPs)—points with known coordinates in both image and object space. Alternatively, the model can remain in a free-network mode, where scaling is applied later using known object dimensions. GCPs can be surveyed with GNSS receivers or total stations, while distances can be measured using electronic distance meters or tape measures.

Photogrammetric parameters vary depending on the camera type. Key factors include the number of images required for computation and processing time, which depends on image resolution and quantity. The density of the final point cloud is primarily influenced by camera sensor size and quality. Once camera parameters are determined, dense **point clouds generation** can be done automatically using image-matching techniques.

Several software solutions support the full photogrammetric workflow, including Photomodeler Scanner and Agisoft Photoscan.

Point Cloud Processing

A point cloud is a collection of data points in a three-dimensional coordinate system, representing the external surface of an object. However, in its raw form, a point cloud is unstructured and unsuitable for direct analysis or design. For practical applications, it must be converted into structured models, such as **polygonal** or **prismatic models**, which provide a simplified representation of the object. These models, however, come with a trade-off—higher generalization often results in reduced detail.

Creating structured models from a point cloud requires a geomatics specialist in specialized software, such as **Leica Cyclone** or **Bentley Pointools**. The level of detail in the final model should be agreed upon between the ordering party and the contractor to meet project requirements.

For BIM applications, point clouds can also be imported directly into BIM software. In Autodesk Revit, for example, most standard point cloud formats can be loaded via the import menu. A 3D model in the desired format can then be generated using BIM tools, ensuring seamless data transfer and allowing designers to choose the appropriate level of detail based on project needs. This approach is particularly beneficial for international projects involving multiple surveying teams, as it streamlines data integration across different workflows.

Application

The most significant use of digital photogrammetry in the building industry is as-built documentation. By utilizing drones, building height and size are no longer constraints, and on-ground activities remain undisturbed. Compared to laser scanning, photogrammetry also enables relatively faster **data collection** and allows for adjustable documentation quality based on **camera specifications**.

Limitations

While photogrammetry is a powerful and efficient technique, it has its limitations:

- **Lower accuracy:** Photogrammetry typically offers **lower accuracy** compared to laser scanning. Unlike laser scanners, which directly measure distances by emitting laser pulses with high temporal resolution, photogrammetry relies on visual data captured **under natural light** and triangulation. As a result, photogrammetric surveys are **less effective in low-light conditions or darkness**, and their accuracy range spans from **a few centimeters to meters**, depending on factors such as image resolution, camera calibration quality, and image overlap. In contrast, laser scanners can achieve accuracy within a few centimeters.
- **Susceptibility to obstructions:** like laser scanning, **obstructed views** can hinder data collection. However, this limitation can be mitigated by capturing images from **multiple vantage points** over different time periods.
- **Complex post-processing:** **point cloud processing** is complex—while software solutions exist, achieving **precise results often requires expert intervention**.
- **Limiting drone regulations:** in some regions, **drone regulations** may impose restrictions on flight operations.

Recommendations

Digital photogrammetry is suitable for all building typologies and is not limited by building height. Although its accuracy is lower than laser scanning, adjustments can be made by selecting the appropriate camera specifications. In the case of INFINITE, photogrammetry proves to be an effective method for creating an overall model of the building to be renovated. Its limitations are relatively minor and can be overcome with careful planning and expert processing.

2.3 Integration of Geomatics in deep renovation process

2.3.1 Specification of objectives

When using advanced geomatics for building documentation, the contract owner must clearly define the demands and requirements to ensure effective communication with the supplier and the production of robust and usable deliverables. Ambiguities in the specifications may lead to misunderstandings and inefficiencies. Requirements depend on the building type, complexity and location, and lead to cost and time optimization.

The following items are key specifications for documentation:

- **Object specification:** documentation level (interior, exterior, surroundings), building size, and address.
- **Level of detail:** desired resolution and model generalization (e.g. smallest visible detail)
- **Model accuracy:** precision requirements, such as less than a centimetre.
- **Coordinate system:** global or local coordinates, which are easier for BIM integration.
- **Requested deliverables:** Point cloud, polygonal or prismatic model, and the specific point cloud data formats for the desired 3D BIM authoring application.

2.3.2 Integration in project phases

The main application of geomatics in INFINITE is the scanning of as-built façades and roofscapes of buildings planned for renovations. This is most relevant in the Concept Design and Planning phases. If necessary, scanning can also be done post-renovation to generate updated as-built drawings for future reference (within maintenance process for instance) and documentation (feeding the Digital Building Logbook for instance).

Ideal project workflow:

1. **Consultation with the ordering party** – Requirement setup
2. **Site Audit** - Site survey and initial data gathering
3. **Method and equipment selection** - Choosing appropriate geomatics tools
4. **In-situ measurements** – Preparation, field survey, and supplementary measurements (e.g. tape measurements)
5. **Data transfer** - Export data from equipment into desired software
6. **Software processing** – Image orientation, point cloud generation (if using photogrammetry), point cloud adjustment, and modelling (if required)

7. **Accuracy verification** - Validation of measurement accuracy
8. **Outcome submission** - Delivery of results to the ordering party

Table 2 outlines the 7 phases of the industrialized renovation process and identifies the stages where geomatics integration is recommended. Specific methods relevant to each phase are listed in the table.

Table 2: Integration of geomatics technologies in different project phases.

Project Phase	Activity	Method
Building Asset Evaluation		
Pre-design	Design fundamentals acquisition	Laser scanning/ Digital photogrammetry
Concept and Executive Design	-	-
Manufacturing and assembling	-	-
Transport, Installation and commissioning	Installation	Manual measurements/ Total station survey
Post-renovation	As-built documentation and quality assessment	Laser scanning/ Digital photogrammetry
Operation and Maintenance	-	-
End-of-life	-	-

2.3.3 Selection of method for surveying

Table 3 provides a comparison between digital photogrammetry and laser scanning, focusing on critical features for decision-making such as equipment costs, site limitations, and time efficiency. It also highlights the common characteristics of the two surveying techniques.

Additional processing information is provided in Table 4. Based on the project phase and survey objectives, a suitable surveying method can be selected. Table 5 indicates the scanning technique recommendations based on specific targets or surveyed objects.

Table 3: Comparison between surveying techniques based on characteristics.

Characteristics	Laser Scanning	Digital Photogrammetry
Equipment	Laser scanner	Reflex camera
Equipment Cost	High (from €40,000)	Low (from €2,000)
Site Limitations	Problems with extremely wet and mirror surfaces	Textured object and fine illumination (daylight) needed
Time Costs	Slower acquisition, faster point cloud production process	Faster acquisition, slower point cloud production process
Data Accuracy	High	Moderate to High
Common Characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-selective, non-contact methods, point cloud creation • Data processing is more time-consuming than data acquisition • Specialized software needed (from €10,000 each) 	

Table 4: Comparison between surveying techniques based on processing.

Processing Factor	Laser Scanning	Digital Photogrammetry
Data Acquisition	Scanning on scan stations, optionally additional measurements	Image acquisition, additional measurement for scaling or georeferencing (distance, GCPs)
Data Export	Exporting point clouds	Downloading images
Processing Workflow for Point Cloud Generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Point cloud registration Point cloud orientation and georeferencing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (Camera calibration) Internal and external orientation, scaling/ georeferencing Point cloud generation
Processing Workflow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Point cloud cleaning (deleting outliers, noise reduction, etc.) Point cloud export (*.asc, *.vtx, *.oj, etc.) Meshing (creating polygonal model) Modelling (creating prismatic model) Model export (*.dxf, *.coe, etc.) 	

Table 5: Technique selection based on objective of mapping.

Mapped Object	Recommended Technique
Building Interior	Laser scanning, Geodetic surveying - total station
Building Exterior, Façade	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Up to 4 floors: Laser scanning, Terrestrial photogrammetry Over 4 floors: Laser scanning, Photogrammetry using UAV/crane
Building Exterior, Roof	Photogrammetry using UAV/crane
Surroundings	Laser scanning, Geodetic surveying - total station
Additional Measurements	Tape, Electronic distance meter, GNSS receiver, Geodetic surveying - total station

2.4 Recommendations for industrialized building renovation

Based on current market research on geomatics technologies (at the date of writing), several recommendations can be made for professionals in the industrialized building renovation sector:

- Laser Scanning and Digital Photogrammetry:** Both techniques are suitable for comprehensive façade surveys. They are faster and more accurate than traditional surveying techniques.
- Technique Selection:** The choice of technique should align with project specifications, requirements, and the preferences of the ordering party. The advantage of laser scanning is that it provides 3D data directly for interpretation. The advantage of digital photogrammetry is that the images hold all the information needed for data reconstruction, and that its equipment is more cost-effective and portable.
- Software Recommendations:** For digital photogrammetry, software like *PhotoModeler Premium* or *Agisoft Meta Shape* are recommended, as they provide high-density point clouds and are compatible with a wide range of cameras, UAVs and LiDAR sensors.

4. **Ground Control Points (GCPs):** The use of GCPs is advised for projects requiring higher accuracy (<5mm) or for measuring larger objects (e.g. residential buildings). Geodetic Total Stations provide fine and quick measurements for establishing GCPs.
5. **Camera Selection:** The use of reflex cameras is recommended for digital photogrammetry, due to their lower noise levels compared to non-reflex cameras, and lower variations compared to laser scanning data.
6. **Optimization of Image Number:** For digital photogrammetry, it is advised to optimize the number of images. A larger number of images increases the risk of model deformation, which may be mitigated by using a greater number of GCPs.

In conclusion, laser scanning emerges as the preferred technique for the digital reconstruction of existing buildings due to its direct provision of 3D data and high accuracy. While both laser scanning and digital photogrammetry offer advantages, the choice of technique should be guided by project specifications and requirements. The use of appropriate software, ground control points, and camera selection can significantly enhance the quality and accuracy of the reconstruction process. However, despite these advancements, the process remains time-consuming, and there is a notable gap in applications that can expedite modeling or effectively resolve misalignments. Further innovations are needed to streamline these processes and fully realize the potential of digital reconstruction technologies. Further innovations in machine learning, particularly in 3D reconstruction, hold promise for addressing these challenges. Advanced Deep Learning techniques, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Transformers Networks (PTv2), along with instance segmentation across 2D and 3D modalities, enable precise identification and reconstruction of class-specific elements. are being explored for their potential to streamline the reconstruction process. These models can learn from large datasets of 3D models and their corresponding 2D images to predict 3D structures accurately. This new frontier of the development integrates algorithms from computer vision, photogrammetry, and CNNs tailored for point-based data, significantly advancing semantic segmentation, instance segmentation, and class-specific reconstruction have shown promising results in generative shape modeling and single-view 3D reconstruction. Integrating these machine learning models into the digital reconstruction workflow could significantly reduce time and improve the accuracy of 3D modeling, ultimately enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of the process.

3 Methodology for assembly and disassembly

3.1 Introduction

Prefabricated industrialized building elements, including the renovation kits developed in INFINITE, feature various building and installation details. These details include areas where elements intersect, or where new components are attached to existing structures, such as at the level of joints. Several innovative building and installation details have been reviewed, along with guidelines and instructions for assembly and disassembly.

For building renovations, it is crucial to assess several characteristics of the building envelope - including thermal insulation, linear thermal bridging, airtightness, watertightness, vapor permeability, fire resistance, and noise insulation - in relation to the methods used for mounting and dismounting elements.

To support the renovation process, building and installation details can be made available digitally (via BIM), enabling direct integration into new designs.

3.2 Literature review on methodologies for DfA/DfD

3.2.1 INFINITE inventory of design tools

An inventory of existing design tools for Design for Assembly (DfA) and Disassembly (DfD) was conducted by Nobatek, in collaboration with HIA, and its results listed in section 3.2.2. Some key observations from this inventory:

1. There is a significant body of research and scientific publications on DfD, although only a small portion of these is included in the inventory.
2. Few *tools* have been developed to support DfD. Among them:
 - i. None is public, or commercialised or massively used.
 - ii. Notable tools include the **RBIM** (Elma Durmisevic) and **Drive 0**, discussed in sections 3.2.2 and 3.2.3.
 - iii. Some tools developed as part of PhD research remain in early stages and cannot yet be considered as usable in practice. Interesting frameworks and toolboxes include **BCI (Building Circularity Indicator)** (Verberne, 2016), and **Disassembly and Deconstruction Analytics System (D-DAS)**.
3. For the DfD approach, the inventory identifies the following:
 - i. Tools (RBIM and Drive 0) that can be used to assess design choices,
 - ii. Frameworks, derived from scientific publications and certification reference documents, offering indicators and design criteria, concepts, and principles to consider. These frameworks are generally broad in scope.
 - iii. Standards, giving indicators and criteria. Two key standards are:
 - a. **CSA Z782-06** - Guideline for Design for Disassembly and Adaptability in Buildings. Updated in 2012.
 - b. **ISO 20887:2020** - Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works - Design for disassembly and adaptability - Principles, requirements and guidance.
 - iv. Guides, giving concepts and principles to follow. One such guide, developed by NBK (AMI FBE), is general, written in French, and applicable at building level.
 - v. The general process used by NBK in the framework of INFINITE is open and based on questioning and challenging the kit designer on various aspects. The main phases of this process are:
 - a. Collecting technical information about the façade kits.

- b. Drawing functional diagrams and analysing them based on DfD criteria.
- c. Questioning and challenging the designer on identified issues (among the activities conducted here, workshops have been held with the INFINITE kits developers).
- d. Revising the diagram.

3.2.2 Listed tools and guidelines

This section provides an overview of key details on the tools and guidelines Identified in the inventory, outlining their developing organization, purpose and methodology, and use potential and relevance to the INFINITE project.

These guiding resources have been categorized into 4 types:

- Tools (Table 6): Software and digital resources for assessment
- Assessment methods (Table 7): Scientific frameworks and scoring systems
- Guidelines (Table 8): General principles and best practices
- Frameworks (Table 9): Conceptual frameworks and structured methodologies

From the full inventory, 8 of the listed resources were selected for further consideration during the INFINITE workshop held with kits developers. They are highlighted in **yellow** in the following tables. These have been shortlisted based on their relevance to the INFINITE development process, their accessibility, and ease-of-use.

Table 6: Overview of DfA/D Resources – Tools

	Name	Organization	Description	Use Potential	Links
Tools	RBIM (Reversible BIM)	· 4D Architects · GTB Lab	Assesses reversibility of components and buildings, reuse potential, impacts, and material connections	· BIM Plug-in · Access currently limited but planned commercial launch	Video Paper
	Drive 0	· ISSO · Drive 0 partners	Assesses the disassembly of details via a scoring system, and allows comparison of detail options in early design	· Excel-based tool · Available for INFINITE partners	
	IconCUR	· Bond University	Maps property decisions in a 3D space over time and supports adaptive reuse planning for existing buildings	· Decision-making tool for property-management · Methodological approach with Adaptive Management (AM) and Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA)	Paper
	D-DAS (Disassembly and Deconstruction Analytics System)		Provides a design-stage assessment of buildings' end-of-life performance.	· Based on BIM-data · Autodesk Revit Plug-in · Low technology readiness level (TRL) · Difficult to apply in INFINITE	Paper
	MIM Tool (Environmental Impact Monitor)	· ABT	Calculates in real-time the environmental impact of Revit-modelled building structures, monitoring material use, carbon footprint and shadow price of various design options	· Tool too large and complex for INFINITE	Web Page
	BCI Gebouw (Building Circularity Index Tool)	· Alba Concepts	Supports and standardizes the calculation of the BCI (below), based updated standard market databases, integrating it with MPG calculations	· Decision-making tool for construction and property-management · Not focused on DfA/D, not directly applicable to INFINITE	Tool Paper Guide

Table 7: Overview of DfA/D Resources - Assessment Methods

	Name	Organization	Description	Use Potential	Links
Assessment Methods	FLEX 3 & 4		Assesses adaptability of buildings to changing needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Practical instrument Does not apply to components 	Paper
	AdaptSTAR Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bond University 	Assesses reusability of future buildings via an adaptive reuse star rating, based on holistic and unified design criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Holistic rating tool Not publicly available Low technology readiness level (TRL) 	Paper
	BCI (Building Circularity Indicator)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TU Eindhoven 	Measures circular potential by giving circularity indicators of products, elements, and buildings. Based on the MCI (below) and the disassembly potential based on their hierarchical building position	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Translates circular principles into Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) Not focused on DFA/D, not directly applicable to INFINITE Also used in RBIM and BCI Gebouw 	Paper
	MCI (Material Circularity Indicator)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ellen MacArthur Foundation Granta Design (EU) 	Identifies circular value of materials and products across life cycles, allows mitigation of material volatility and supply risks, and could (with the MI: product intelligence package) analyse env., regulatory and supply chain risks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Excel-based tool Available in an easy-to-use format Too general for INFINITE Applicable as quick scan tool in early design stages 	Web Page
	Circular Buildings Disassembly Potential v2.0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DGBC NL Alba Concepts 	Determines the demountability index for building elements, covering the Structure, Skin, Services, and Space plan layers of the layers of brand.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drafted for integration into existing tools (BREEAM-NL and GPR Gebouw) Interesting and easy method Concepts similar as in RBIM 	Web Page

Table 8: Overview of DfA/D Resources - Guidelines

	Name	Organization	Description	Use Potential	Links
Guidelines	DGNB Criterion TEC 1.6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DGNB 	Sets general indicators for DfA/D, as criteria for DGNB certification for disassembly and recovery.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lacks technical assessment method Not applicable to INFINITE kit development 	Criteria Set
	Level(s) - Indicator 2.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU 	Checklist of design aspects for adaptive reuse and deconstruction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focus on adaptive reuse of existing buildings, not DFA/D strategies 	Policy Report
	BREEAM UK New Construction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BREEAM UK 	Sets criteria for responsible sourcing of products, design durability and resilience, and DfA for the BREEAM rating	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General set of guidelines, not a technical one Focus on new buildings 	Tech Manual
	CSA Z782-06	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CSA (Canada) 	Sets a conceptual framework for DfA/D principles to achieve disassembly at building level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General aspects (definitions, examples, metrics), not a technical framework 	Guide
	"Guide d'aide à la conception pour la démontabilité"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nobatek 	Defines general principles for integrating DfA/D into designs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Applicable as base during the design process 	Guide

Table 9: Overview of DfA/D Resources - Frameworks

	Name	Organization	Description	Use Potential	Links
Frameworks	CCEF (Circular Construction Evaluation Framework)	· Dams et al.	Scores circularity at element or building levels (using two sets of indicators), prioritizing standardization, connection reversibility and material reuse	· Easy-to-use at a component and building level	Paper
	System for Analysis, Design for Disassembly and Recycling	· Schwedea & Störl	Database-backed language and approach for supporting design for deconstruction and recycling. Based on Recycling Graph editor, E. Durmisevic factors, and German standards (e.g. DIN 8593-0, DIN 8580), BNB-criterion.	· Constructive language for development of design methods and tools · Interesting method, but not yet implemented in computational modelling tools.	Paper
	INFINITE General Process (T4.8)	· Nobatek	Guided INFINITE designers on integrating DfA/D principles in the development process	· Applicable as base for design development in INFINITE	Web Page

3.2.3 INFINITE Workshop

As part of INFINITE, an internal workshop was conducted on October 5, 2022, to guide INFINITE project partners in selecting appropriate Design for Assembly (DfA) and Design for Disassembly (DfD) tools and methods for their development process.

Hosted by HIA and Nobatek, the 1.5-hour workshop aimed to inform participants about relevant tools and facilitate their integration into the later stages of technology and pilot project development. Although project designs were already underway, the workshop sought to ensure that DfA/D tools and frameworks could still be leveraged beyond the INFINITE project's immediate scope.

A detailed description of the workshop, process and results may be referred to under Annex 1.

Methodology

The workshop preparation involved the shortlisting of 8 tools from the detailed inventory based on their applicability, accessibility, and relevance to both technology developers and pilot project designers. Participants received a table overview of the tools and an interactive Miro board framework one week in advance to familiarize themselves with the content. The tools were categorized into BIM-plugins, standards, and frameworks, with an emphasis on their outputs, such as circularity assessment, disassembly potential indicators, and reversibility analysis.

The workshop was structured into two key parts:

1. **Presentation of relevant tools:** Experts introduced Drive 0 and R-BIM, demonstrating their capabilities and applications. Additional frameworks, including the Building Circularity Indicator (BCI) and Disassembly Potential Measurement Method (Dutch Green Building Council (DGBC)), were also discussed.
2. **Interactive session on Miro:** Participants engaged in two exercises to explore challenges, identify tool requirements, and assess potential applications for INFINITE.

Exercise 1: Identifying challenges and needs

Participants listed challenges in applying DfA/D and circularity tools. These included:

- Difficulty quantifying improvements in assembly/disassembly design.
- Lack of trained personnel for DfA/D analysis.
- Complexity of tools and time-consuming manual applications.
- Integration challenges with BIM environments.

- Need for clear cost-benefit and environmental impact assessments.

Exercise 2: Tool preferences and applications

In two parallel sessions (technology providers and pilot project teams), partners identified preferred tools and their applications, concluding that Drive 0 and RBIM were the most suitable options.

Outcome

The workshop provided valuable insights into tool selection and DfA/D implementation challenges, leading to several key takeaways:

- **Tool Integration in BIM:** Participants emphasized the need for easy-to-use tools that integrate seamlessly into BIM workflows.
- **Quantifying DfA/D benefits:** A strong need was identified for methods that demonstrate cost savings, reduced maintenance needs, and environmental impacts.
- **Regulatory landscape:** Since DfA/D assessments are not mandatory, standardization and incentivization (e.g., public grants) could drive adoption.
- **Preferred tools & next steps:**
 - **Drive 0:** Recommended for early-stage design assessment due to its user-friendly interface and ability to evaluate connection details and circularity scores.
 - **RBIM:** Suitable for detailed design stages, allowing BIM-based circularity assessments even without full detailing of fasteners.

By aligning tools with project phases and needs, the workshop established a framework for DfA/D decision-making within INFINITE, reinforcing its role in advancing sustainable and circular building practices.

3.2.4 Selected Tools

3.2.4.1 Drive 0

Disassembly is a crucial factor in making building construction circular by enabling product reuse (thereby extending product lifespan) and improving building adaptability and maintenance (thereby extending building lifespan).

The Drive 0 tool assesses the disassembly potential of construction details, more specifically:

- **Benchmarking:** The Circularity Indicators (CI) for Detachability or Design for Disassembly (DfD) are considered more suitable for standard details than the Material Index (MI) or Reusability Index (RI).
- **Methodology:** The assessment method is based on the '*Circular Buildings, measurement method detachability*' developed by Alba concepts in collaboration with DGBC and W/E advisors, commissioned by the Dutch Ministry of the Interior and the Circular Construction Economy Transition Agenda.

The method evaluates detachability using 4 key factors:

- Connection Type (TV)
- Accessibility of the Connection (ToV)
- Integration (DK)
- Edge Confinement (RA)

Each factor is assigned a score between 0.1 and 1.0, where 0.1 represents the lowest level of detachability and 1.0 the highest.

The first two factors (TV and ToV) determine the detachability index of the connection (LIC_n), while the last two factors (DK and RA) define the detachability index of the composition (LIS_n). Together, these indices provide an overall measure of a product's disassembly potential (LIP_n). The equations used for the calculation of these detachability indices are the following:

$$LIC_n = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{TV_n} + \frac{1}{ToV_n}}$$

containing:

LIC_n detachability index of the connection of product or element n :

TV_n type of connection of product or element n

ToV_n accessibility of the connection of product or element n

$$LIS_n = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{DK_n} + \frac{1}{RO_n}}$$

containing:

LIS_n detachability index of composition of product or element n :

DK_n Integration of product or element n

RO_n edge confinement of product or element n

$$LIP_n = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{LIC_n} + \frac{1}{LIS_n}}$$

containing:

LIP_n detachability index of the product or element n :

LIC_n detachability index of the connection of product or element n :

LIS_n detachability index of composition of product or element n :

- **Visualization:** To enhance clarity, the detachability scores are translated into a color-coded system applied to the reference details. This provides a direct visual insight into the detachability of different elements, making Drive 0 a useful tool for analysis during the design process. The following figure (Figure 2) illustrates the correlation between the color code and the detachability score.

Figure 2: Drive 0 - color code

- **Example Detail:** Below is an example construction detail highlighting the detachability potential at the end-of-life scenario (Figure 3), along with a detailed breakdown of the corresponding calculation of the detachability index (Figure 4).
- **Application:** The proposed method demonstrates the potential of assessing the detachability performance of components, offering a valuable framework for improving the assembly of building components. The visualization of the detachability performance into the 'Performance Layer' of the 'Reference Details' supports designers in incorporating Design for Disassembly (DfD) principles into their projects. By optimizing detachability, designers can enhance building longevity through maintenance and transformation.

Figure 3: Example detail with performance detachability for the end-of-life scenario (ISSO, 2021)

End-of-life	201.0.3.1BENV	Assessment	Score
1 Sill	On inner cavity leaf	Assessment: Average	0,53
Type of connection	0,80 Screw	Connection with added elements	
Accessibility of connection	0,40 Accessible with additional operations with partially repairable damage		
2 Aluminum sill	On window frame	Assessment: Good	0,89
Type of connection	0,80 Screw	Connection with added elements	
Accessibility of connection	1,00 Freely accessible without extra actions		
3 Outer cavity leaf	On inner cavity leaf	Assessment: Very bad	0,10
Type of connection	0,10 Chemical anchors	Hard chemical bond	
Accessibility of connection	0,10 Inaccessible – irreparable damage to the product or surrounding products		
4 Insulation	On inner cavity leaf	Assessment: Excellent	0,89
Type of connection	0,80 Connection with added elements	Connection with added elements	
Accessibility of connection	1,00 Freely accessible without extra actions		
5 Window frame	On inner cavity leaf	Assessment: Excellent	0,89
Type of connection	0,80 Connection with added elements	Connection with added elements	
Accessibility of connection	1,00 Freely accessible without extra actions		
6 Inner cavity leaf	Not applicable		

Figure 4: Detailed calculation of the detachability index for the example detail (ISSO, 2021)

3.2.4.2 R-BIM

As per our assessment, R-BIM is one of the most advanced tools available in the market for assessing the reversibility potential of buildings and their components. It evaluates the impact of disassembly and reuse scenarios, therefore supporting circular design strategies.

Developed over several years through research initiatives such as BAMB (BAMB, n.d.) and Digital Deconstruction (Digital Deconstruction, n.d.), the tools were led by Elma Durmisevic at TU Delft and then at 4D Architects. Currently, due to its complexity, R-BIM is exclusively used by 4D Architects for design and engineering services.

Originally designed to analyze the reversibility and reuse potential of existing buildings, R-BIM aims to optimize deconstruction and material recovery strategies. It has been applied in various projects, including the renovation of the Roman Museum of Heerlen in the Netherlands (Oztan, 2022) and multiple pilot projects under the Digital Deconstruction initiative.

More specifically:

- **Methodology:** To evaluate the reversibility and reuse potential, R-BIM integrates in its algorithm a range of engineering indicators and concepts, including:
 - Element clustering and independencies,
 - Connection types and layers,
 - Assembly and disassembly sequencing.

These principles were first outlined in the *Transformable Building Structures: Design for Disassembly as a Way to Introduce Sustainable Engineering to Building Design & Construction* (Durmisevic, 2006).

- **Visualization:** The R-BIM tool features a 3D visualization interface, a comprehensive inventory of building elements, with an assessment of their reversibility and reuse potential. Users can explore different reuse and recycling scenarios, with impact dashboards quantifying factors such as CO₂ savings and material recovery rates.
- **Application and Workflow:** The tool requires BIM models generated according to R-BIM specifications, as inputs and work interface. Users then characterize building elements (e.g. material), defining their interdependencies, and connections. By leveraging BIM modeling, it supports an iterative design process that integrates Design for Disassembly (DfD) principles. While R-BIM was initially developed for existing buildings, it is then also applicable to new designs.

If the BIM model meets the specifications defined by 4D Architects, an initial analysis of a construction system can be conducted for an estimated budget of approximately €5,000.

- **Example:** Below are illustrations featuring the R-BIM tool for a façade element (Figure 5) and a roof (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Illustration of R-BIM tool on facade element (Source: 4DArchitects in Digital Deconstruction)

Figure 6: Illustration of R-BIM tool on roof construction (Source: 4DArchitects in Digital Deconstruction)

3.3 Recommendations from INFINITE project

For an impactful implementation of Design for Assembly and Disassembly (DfA/D) strategies, it is crucial to quantify their benefits. Measuring the reduction in repair and maintenance needs and associated cost savings of different DfA/D choices, as well as assessing their impact on the CO₂ footprint of a project will be a critical factor in decision-making.

Establishing a clear link between circular design type strategies and environmental impact would enhance the credibility and market potential of INFINITE solutions. One way to achieve this is by integrating a standardized DfA/D scoring system within the BIM environment, also allowing design choices to be directly correlated with Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) outcomes.

Moreover, since renovation kits and products in the INFINITE project are designed for disassembly, there is an opportunity for project partners to extend their business models by incorporating repair and maintenance services, fostering long-term engagement with clients.

3.3.1 Recommended DfA/D Tools and Methods

During the workshop, there was a strong consensus that circular design decision-making should not overcomplicate, and rather complement, the design process. Therefore, a phased approach to tool selection was recommended, such as:

- **Early design stages:** Use of simple and straightforward tools, such as Drive 0, for assessing detachability and circularity potential in conceptual design iterations.
- **Later design stages:** Use of BIM-integrated tools like R-BIM, which provide detailed reversibility analysis and support advanced decision-making.

Based on workshop insights, the following **matrix of recommendations** outlines suitable tools and methods for different project phases:

Table 10: Recommended DfA/D tools and methods per project phase

No.	Project Phase	Description	Recommendation	Purpose
1	Project Initiation/ Viability Phase	Definition of project type and scope: adaptive reuse or new construction	· Flex 3.0 or 4.0	Reuse potential assessment of the project
2	Concept Design & Planning	Exploration of different design iterations for products/ elements	· CSA Z782-06 (Guideline for DfD/A in Buildings) · Guide d'aide à la conception pour la démontabilité (Guidelines for DfD) · Drive 0	Guidelines and scoring for DfA/D decision-making and early design comparison of initial iterations (Drive 0)
3	Statutory Approval	Engagement with local authorities for compliance	· Building Circularity Indicator (BCI) · Circular Buildings Disassembly Potential Measurement Method V2.0 (DGBC)	Overall assessment of the circularity potential of the building
4	Detailed Design	Finalization of construction drawings, specifications, and documents	· R-BIM · Disassembly and Deconstruction Analytics System (D-DAS)	BIM-integrated and detailed assessment of critical disassembly criteria
5	Construction, Delivery & Installation	On-site activities	x	Guidelines on assembly incorporated into design documents and construction drawings
6	Operation & Maintenance	Building use phase	x	Guidelines on repair and maintenance incorporated in project documents and construction drawings
7	End-of-Life	Disassembly, materials recovery and reuse/ reassemble viability of material.	x	Guidelines on disassembly and material recovery incorporated in project documents and construction drawings

By following this structured approach, INFINITE partners can enhance decision-making, reduce environmental impact, and strengthen circular construction practices through practical and data-driven methodologies.

4 Conclusions

This report underscores the importance of advanced geomatics and DfA/D methodologies in optimizing industrialized building renovation. By leveraging high-precision 3D scanning and structured design strategies, the INFINITE project aims to streamline retrofit processes, enhance circularity, and improve lifecycle efficiency.

Key takeaways include:

- The integration of laser scanning and digital photogrammetry into BIM workflows significantly enhances accuracy and efficiency in renovation planning.
- DfA/D tools like Drive 0 and R-BIM provide practical solutions for evaluating and improving disassembly potential and reuse strategies.
- Standardization and regulatory support are necessary to drive widespread adoption of circular design principles.
- Further research is needed to refine automated data processing, simplify tool applications, and establish consistent assessment frameworks.

Moving forward, the INFINITE project will focus on embedding these methodologies into industrial workflows, promoting interdisciplinary collaboration, and advocating for policy measures that support circular and sustainable building practices. By addressing existing challenges and leveraging emerging technologies, the project contributes to the transformation of the renovation sector towards a more resilient and resource-efficient future.

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Annex 1: INFINITE workshop on DfA/D resources

A1.1 Introduction

As part of Task 3.5.2, an internal workshop was conducted on October 5, 2022, to familiarize partners with available DfD and DfA tools and facilitate the selection of the most relevant tools and resources for their needs. The workshop, jointly led by HIA and Nobatek, lasted 1.5 hours and included both presentations and interactive discussions.

A comprehensive inventory of assessment of tools and methods had been developed through Task 3.5 and Task 4.8, based on partner inputs. While the technology and pilot projects had already progressed, this workshop aimed to highlight tools that could support further development and refinement of technologies within and beyond the INFINITE project.

A1.2 Methodology

A1.2.1 Pre-Workshop Preparation

Eight tools were shortlisted from the detailed inventory (in section 3.2.2 above) based on their applicability, accessibility, and relevance to technology developers and pilot project designers.

A table summarizing these tools, along with a structured Miro board, was shared with participants a week before the workshop. The tools were categorized into BIM plugins, standards, and frameworks, with an overview of their outputs (e.g., circularity assessment, disassembly potential, reversibility assessment).

A1.2.2 Workshop Structure

The workshop was divided into two main parts:

1. **Presentation of Relevant Tools and Resources:** Introduction to tools such as RBIM and Drive 0, including their functionalities, benefits, and practical applications.
2. **Interactive Session on Miro:** Hands-on exercises allowing participants to explore tool relevance, identify challenges, and discuss their expectations from DfA/D tools. The detailed screenshots of this Miro board workshop session may be found under Annex 2 below.

A1.3 Workshop Proceedings

A1.3.1 Presentation of Tools

The session began with an introduction to Task 3.5.2 and the objectives of the workshop, followed by an explanation of the inventory development process. Despite being developed by different agencies for various applications, it was emphasized that most of the tools share common scientific concepts.

Specific relevant tools were then addressed:

- **Drive 0 Tool:** Presented by Peter Op 't Veld from HIA, demonstrating how it is used, using practical examples.
- **R-BIM Tool:** Presented by Benjamin LACLAU from Nobatek, accompanied by a brief video demonstration.

- **Additional Guidelines & Frameworks:** Overview of the Building Circularity Indicator (BCI) and the Disassembly Potential Measurement Method (DGBC)

The presentation of the tools was then followed by the Miro workshop session.

A1.3.2 Miro Session: Exercise 1

In order to identify the tools and resources relevant for each INFINITE partner, the goal of the first exercise was to first identify their respective needs with regards to DfA/D resources that would enhance the circularity of their products.

Participants were asked to list their struggles with DfA/D and circularity tools, as well as their desired outputs from such tools. The detailed Miro input is found in the screenshots under Annex 2. Below is a summary of the key insights gathered from the different companies:

	Company	Type	Struggles	Needs
1	Bouygues Construction	Construction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • unable to quantify improvements towards assembly/disassembly design 	
2	Casa Spa	Property management		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • help in detailing for assembly
3	Rubner Holzbau	Timber engineering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • not having trained staff to perform such analysis • very low experience with DfD approach • generate benefits by applying the DfD approach without complicating the design/execution process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • evaluate options for re-use of applied solutions • reuse potential of material/components
4	Eurac Research	Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate the DfD potential of different design choices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantitative interdisciplinary scoring system (sustainability, business)
5	Greendelta	LCA/ LCC consultants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Companies not used to integrate these tools at early stage of technology development • Time consuming to manually apply standards/methodologies to each component in a building (tool and BIM integration is the right direction) • Missing Interdisciplinary professional figures (engineers with expertise in DfA/D and design) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connection between DfA/D recommendations and implications on costs and environmental impacts • Better understanding of end-of-life pathways for construction components
6	Vortice	Ventilation systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • not having trained staff to perform such analysis 	
7	Grunstattgrau	Green wall systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A big range of different systems and components is available on the market (e.g. materials, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • greening companies could be good target group, since they already are attentive to

			<p>forms.) - hard to generalise, have to focus on specific examples or at least categories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • especially for green facades (eg. living walls) not a lot of data on end-of-life scenarios, also for green roofs rare • WHEN is the end of life? very much depends on effort and care put into greening/ irrigation system • haven't done enough research so far on DfDA of greening components 	<p>sustainability aspect (primarily recycled plastics used e.g. for green roof drainage)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • bigger greening companies offer BIM models and sometimes certificates (eg. C2C) • knowledge about disassembling components • possibility to reuse plants at the end of life?? usually they develop over time and adapt to location, alternatives to composting? • can established plants (eg. sedum on green roofs) be used for new green roofs? • Or substrate components could be prepared again, have to check with companies if this is already being done
8	Generalitat Valencia IVE	Institution		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of classification
9	Nobatek	Sustainability consultants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complexity of the tools and methods • No regulation defining level to reach and targeting method to follow • Can consider all the parameters that impact DfD • Get simple assessment methods and tools compatible with BIM that can be used by non-expert people • Incentive to push the DfD approach in a positive way 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circularity potential assessment • Maintenance or repairing support • Highlight what part of the product or systems are problematic • Give recognized level of disassembling • Ideally automatically propose ideas of improvements
10	One Team	Technology solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lot of data to input by experts (tech providers) • how to make relationships btw elements\DfD processes in an easy way (collect data, link data, etc) • lot of data to be collected in the preliminary design (when changes are feasible) but -as preliminary- all this data usually is not available • a common DfD framework of concepts is needed to share same parameters\processes\ to be used by the AEC market • open-source approach to share common practices, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • include data in the BIM libraries • system to compare different solutions to change design in the preliminary phase • mapping btw BIM elements and DfD data

11	Huygen	Sustainability consultants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • an easy to apply assessment method, not too 'scientific' • Is a certain rate of standardization necessary or not? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a simple connection with BIM, (to be used for controlling production lines and for design)
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A discussion followed, where partners elaborated on their identified challenges and needs. These insights formed the foundation for the second exercise.

A1.3.3 Miro Session: Exercise 2

Partners were divided into two parallel sessions based on their focus areas (technology development vs. pilot projects). They were asked to list their preferred tools out of the inventory list, specifying their potential applications. If similar results were received for the choice of preferred tools, the applications varied.

Key takeaways included:

- **Preferred Tools:** Drive 0 and RBIM emerged as the most relevant tools.
- **Potential Applications in INFINITE:**
 - Show DfA/D potential in BIM models.
 - Score different design options.
 - Support and validate demo case designs.
 - Assess maintenance/repair frequency and costs.
 - Develop new client services related to maintenance and repair.

A1.4 Key Discussion Points

Key discussion takeaways from the workshop are the following:

- **Regulations for DfA/D:** Participants noted the lack of strict regulations requiring circularity assessment. As a result, the available tools and methods are only used voluntarily by a select number of companies.
- **BIM-Integration:** All partners emphasized the importance of ease-of-use and seamless BIM integration to ensure practical and optimal adoption of DfA/D tools.
- **Quantifying benefits of DfA/D strategies:** To encourage adoption, it was agreed that demonstrating tangible benefits (e.g., reduced maintenance costs, environmental impact) to clients and product developers is essential. Linking DfA/D assessments and their quantified benefits with Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) holds high potential in increasing sustainable choices in the industry.
- **Incentivisation of Circular and DfA/D strategies:** There was consensus on the need for incentives to encourage DfA/D adoption, such as financial benefits or regulatory advantages. Currently, some municipalities (e.g., in Spain) have started linking circularity benchmarks to public grant eligibility.
- **Standardization of tools and assessment criteria:** The need for standardization was highlighted to ensure consistency across the industry, which may be required if circularity were to become statutory requirement. A common DfD framework would support broader adoption.

A1.5 Conclusions for INFINITE and Next Steps

In the context of INFINITE, the key aspects for the selection of DfD/A tools and methods were:

- Quantification of benefits (e.g. reduction in maintenance and repair costs, reduction in environmental costs) would support informed selection between design iterations.
- DfA/D assessment scores and methods could be integrated in BIM models.
- Demonstration and comparison of DfA/D strategies' benefits would give more credibility to the Infinite solutions' market potential.
- Additional services, such as repairs and maintenance, could be proposed by partners to the clients, as part of their business models.
- Circular design processes must not overcomplicate the design process and rather complement it in an effort towards a more sustainable design.

The workshop successfully provided participants with insights into the most relevant DfA/D tools and their potential applications. Moving forward:

- Drive 0 will be promoted for early-stage design due to its simplicity and comparative scoring capabilities. It allows the selection of various connection details between elements, and their individual scoring for a comparative total score.
- R-BIM will be explored further for detailed assessments during the detail design stage, assessing the circularity of user-defined connection details in BIM models. Although BIM models may not have connection details (i.e. nuts, bolts, screws, etc.), the R-BIM plug-in allows users to select the connection type at each junction as analysis input data.
- Partners will continue discussions on how to integrate these tools into their workflows.

By streamlining tool usage and aligning them with existing BIM workflows, INFINITE can enhance the practical implementation of circular strategies in the built environment.

Annex 2: Miro board workshop session

Struggles of the partners and desired outcomes from DfD tools/methods

COMPANY NAME	STRUGGLES	DESIRED OUTPUTS FROM DFD/ DFA TOOLS
EXAMPLE : COMPANY ABC	STREAMLINING THE DESIGN FOR ASSEMBLY/DIGASS NEXT TO WHOLE DESIGN PROCESS	CIRCULARITY ASSESSMENT OF BUILDING/ PRODUCT
		BUILDING PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT
	unable to quantify improvements towards assembly/disassemble design	
		BUILDING ADAPTABILITY help in detailing for assembly?
	not having trained staff to perform such analysis very low experience with DfD approach generate benefits by applying the DfD approach without complicating the design/execution process	evaluate options for re-use of applied solutions REUSE POTENTIAL OF MATERIAL/ COMPONENTS
	Evaluate the DfD potential of different design choices	Quantitative interdisciplinary scoring system (sustainability, business)
	Companies not used to integrate these tools at early stage of technology developments Time consuming to manually verify standard/compliance in each component in a building level and integrate in the right direction Missing interdisciplinary professional figures/beginners with expertise on DfD and design	Connection between DfD recommendations and indicators on costs and environmental impacts Better understanding of end of life pathways for construction components
	Big range of different systems and components available on market (e.g. materials, costs, ...). Hard to generate. Have to focus on specific materials or at least categories especially for green building being health for a lot of data on end of life recovery, which green results are When is end of life very much depends on effort and care put into greening/irrigation systems haven't done enough research so far on DFA of greening components	greening companies could be good origin groups, since they already are attentive to sustainability aspect (generally recycled plastics, visible e.g. for green roof drainage) bigger greening companies offer BIM models and sometimes certificates (e.g. CIC) knowledge about disassembling components possibility to reuse plants at end of life? usually they develop green roof and plant containers, alternatives to composting? can established plants (e.g. sodum) on green roofs be used for new green roofs? Or individual components could be removed again, have to check with companies if this is already being done

		Level of classification
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complexity of the tools and methods No regulation defining level to reach and targeting method to follow Can consider all the parameters that enter into account in DID Get simple assessment methods and tools compatible with data that can be used by non expert people Incentive to push the DID approach in a positive way 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circularity potential assessment Maintenance or repairing support Highlight what part of the product or systems are problematic Give recognized level of disassembling Identify automatically propose ideas of improvements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> lot of data to input by experts (each province) how to make relationships between accessibility, proximity or energy (build data, loc. data, etc) no common data standard to permit comparison of accessibility, energy, etc. (no common data, no energy, no accessibility) a common DID framework of variables to model (for the same parameters/variables will be used by the AC market) open source approach in whole assessment process, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> include data in the DID database system to compare different solutions to model data in the preliminary phase creating new DID, systems and DID data
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> an easy to apply assessment method, not too 'scientific' is a certain rate of standardisation necessary or not? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a simple connection with BIM, (to be used for controlling, production lines and for design)

TECHNOLOGIES : TOOL MAPPING BASED ON OUTPUTS EXPECTED

COMPANY NAME	PREFERRED TOOLS	POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS OF THESE TOOLS FOR INFINITE AND OTHER
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 Drive 0 1 RBIM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Score different development options Show in BIM the DID potential on the real buildings
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tolls like Drive 0 seems more useful for a first application preferences for tools that offer the possibility to enter data quickly, without having to detail every single component 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> support the executive design for demo cases, evaluating alternatives for the kits application
	<p>Drive 0 tool</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> not having trained staff to perform such analysis in any case to evaluate the impact of assembly and disassembly of our unit inside the facade kit can be useful adopt an easier tool as first method of interaction
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 RBIM 2 Drive 0 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide benefits quantification (for instance potential maintenance/repairing costs reduction) Propose new services to clients and partners improve the "qualification" of the entities kits for INFINITE if we manage to explain the benefits get from conducting this approach

PILOT PROJECTS : TOOL MAPPING BASED ON OUTPUTS EXPECTED

PILOT PROJECT LOCATION	PREFERRED TOOLS	POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS OF THESE TOOLS FOR INFINITE
SLOVENIA		
FRANCE		
ITALY		

**ARCHIVE
Struggles**

1. Inability to quantify and evaluate improvements towards DfA/D in early design stages
2. Lack of experience in integrating DfA/D in conventional development processes
3. Complexity of available assessment tools and methods.
4. Complexity due to large number of materials and components, difficult to generalize
5. Time consumed in application of standards/ methods for each component
6. Not having trained interdisciplinary staff with expertise in DfA/D analysis
7. Lack of regulations and benchmarks for DfA/D process.
8. Complexity and volume of data required to standardize processes.

Needs:

1. Evaluation and comparison of early design choices in terms of DfA/D and reuse potential.
2. Simple assessment methods and tools that are BIM compatible and can be used by non-experts.
3. Standardized and open-source tools and frameworks
4. Interdisciplinary scoring system
5. Incentives to push DfA/D in the industry
6. Research on EoL and DfA/D potential of green walls and plants.
7. DfA/D related data to be included in the BIM libraries
8. Data on cost and environmental impact of DfA/D choices.
9. Support on maintenance and repairing; predictive maintenance of problematic parts